

SDGine
for Healthy People and Cities

A research and innovation platform for the SDGs

HR EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH

POLITÉCNICA

UNIVERSIDAD
POLITÉCNICA
DE MADRID

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 945139

A programme at UPM to attract outstanding talent to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDGine is a research and innovation action to develop **transformative technologies and innovation** for healthy people and cities.

SDGine is a **60-month H2020 COFUND project** funded by the European Union under a Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement. The action, with an overall budget of 1,952,640.00€, will run from 1st October 2020 to 31st September 2025.

SDGine gives **12 Early-Stage Researchers** the opportunity to complete **International and Industrial Doctorates at UPM**. The researchers will have the chance to complete, with a 36-month employment contract, a PhD degree co-supervised by a UPM professor and a responsible from one of the companies that are participating in this project.

In Collaboration with UPM, Companies should

- Establish and co-supervise the training, research and work plans.
- Provide the necessary support for the development of the PhD thesis.
- Promote mobility (secondments of at least 3 months in international locations to obtain the International Doctorate).
- Encourage training (conference attendance and participation).
- State the forms of use and exploitation of results.

Benefits for Companies

- Attraction of talent adapted to the needs of the company
- Training of (future) employees in cutting-edge technologies
- Access to UPM research groups and facilities. Access into high-added value research lines, knowledge and expertise
- R&D&I development in start-up and emerging companies
- Tax benefits from investment in R&D&I Creation of strategic alliances

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) is making a firm commitment to position the SDGs in its main fields of action:

Research: aligning researchers and research groups with SDGs, training researchers, and enabling multi- stakeholder partnerships.

Training: including SDGs in educational plans, specialized training Master “Strategies and Technologies for Development” and Specific Training Course “SDGs and cities”.

Technology transference through University - Industry Chairs and volunteering.

For more details and information go to www.sdGINE.eu
Contact us at sdGINE@upm.es